

Lighthouse Academy

***Is There No Place for the Word
Stability in Macbeth?***

Mr. Hussam Shamma

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Abstract

This paper, wearing the leans of deconstruction, investigates the unstable world of Shakespeare's Macbeth. It attempts to use deconstruction as a reading strategy to dig deep down inside the crust of the bloody story, allowing meanings to spring up from everywhere. This paper consists of three parts: the first part, the introduction, introduces the strategic way of reading; deconstruction, and its founding father, Jacques Derrida. The body of this paper comes next putting theory to practice. Finally, the results and findings of this article.

Keywords: Deconstruction, transcendental signifier, Western culture, undesirability, meaning, supplement

“I speak only one language, and it is not my own.”

Jacques Derrida, Monolingualism of the Other: or, The Prosthesis of Origin

Hussam Shamma

Lighthouse Academy

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Waging war against the co-called authority and ruling power of the Western thought, which enslaved the text by one stable and fundamental meaning from the foundations of the Greek civilization until the present time, Jacques Derrida Stages his deliberate endeavor to disturb and shake the whole existence of the Western assumptions and beliefs. He clearly launched his philosophical coup against the governmental legacy of the classical concepts and ideologies at a conference in Johns Hopkins University in 1966 America, where he introduced his intricate ideas and terms through presenting his paper *Structure, sign, and System* (Bressler 71). No more of the ultimate being that rules and confines the way we perceive a literary work.

In nutshell, Jacques Derrida proposes an alternative approach to textual analysis, which he dubs not a school, or a theory of criticism but simply a 'strategic device.' It is a kind of lineage steps and techniques that could be applied to a literary text, which contains Western philosophical and conceptual oppositions, in certain sequence, but not necessarily in the same order. Most importantly is to recognize the binary oppositions found in a text; for example, you may encounter the light/dark couple in the text, and, of course, lightness compared to darkness is much more preferable and appeals to our consciousness as something privileged and better than darkness. This hierarchy is inherited from the Western culture as something unassailable and exists outside language.

After locating these opposite elements, reverse the hierarchy and postpone the meaning of the old privileged term for a moment in order to be able to value the new hierarchy. Then explain how one element in the binary of the Western thought exists at the expense of the other, then try to show that the two elements are equal, in a sense, and cannot exist or standalone each one by itself. By now, the relationship between the two

elements of the hierarchy is no more a stable one, and stands not any constraints or limitations on the behalf of European thought. In addition; leave the relationship between them indecidable and uncertain, avoiding being logo-centric with the newly-built hierarchy by making each one of the hierarchy dependent on the other and instead of an opposite element, a supplemental element (Bressler 81).

Finally, be objective examining and evaluating the new couple. Do not side any one of the hierarchy by being conventionally and subconsciously inclined to prefer one element above the other. Accept all the possible approaches to a meaning as valid and legitimate, for Derrida himself believes that it is impossible for a reader to arrive at an interpretation that establishes an absolutely certain relationship between a text and a meaning because any use of language unavoidably involves a countless of contradictory signifiers that serve to operate as an open ended circle of meanings. “No concept, Derrida maintains, is beyond the dynamic instability of language which disseminates an infinite number of possible meanings with each written or spoken utterance” (Tyson 56). Signifiers now are like the leaves of marigold dispersed perpetually through the rough winds of language, and none of us is able to trammel up the wild words of today's discourse.

Applying these steps to a Shakespearean work such as *Macbeth*, Deconstruction may seem easier to be grasped and understood. It is noteworthy to mention that deconstruction's infection first started to transmit itself to the world of Shakespeare in the early 1970s, when many critics extolled the unique suitability of this approach to the 'Bard's work'. “Gary Waller records sending a —ripple of apprehension around the gatherings, solemn and celebratory alike when he raised the notion of deconstructing Shakespeare at the Stratford-upon-Avon International Shakespeare Convention in 1978” (Wittek 5). “Having spoken openly—even though along with others—of — decentering the bard, I strolled to the parish church to see if the still center of our deliberations, the bard's bones, had moved. They lay, undisturbed, and I felt not cursed, but liberated” (Waller 21). Despite the fact of the ingenious mind of Shakespeare, Gary Waller celebrated his liberation of the text from its alleged father and creator, which considered to be at that time a kind of literary blasphemy; no man was brave enough to think of “decentering the bard.” We should not abide ourselves by the conventions and ideologies that we inherited from our

ancestors, and we should always put these assumptions of the past into question no matter who the writer is.

Shakespeare the dramatist is more known for his play's legacy than his poems. His plays in general and his tragedies in particular, for instance, have been the focus of thousands of critical studies, and countless number of articles, books, anthologies and many more were written and compiled by international scholars, writers and even students. One of his greatest and most bewildering tragedies is *Macbeth*, where certainty is removed from a world full of contradictions. Therefore, Mesmerized by the conspicuous binary oppositions that pervade and establish the whole atmosphere of Shakespeare's *Macbeth*, the following paper concisely investigates and dissects the unstable and shaky world of the play, divorcing the text from the conventional and logocentric way of perceiving one limited meaning. As well as highlighting the possibility of the text to be a dispenser of countless meanings and interpretations by utilizing a 'strategic device' and technique of reading, interpreting and writing.

Natural and unnatural binary oppositions are clearly summoned to be subverted in the shaky world of *Macbeth*. The natural world is related to the tangible world and therefore reality whereas the unnatural is beyond the physical world and thus called illusion, and the whole play is mainly about what is natural and what is not. Clearly enough is the fact that the natural world is mingled with the political structure and the hierarchy that exists in the play. As shown in the play, there is a strong bond between the political order and the natural one, and once Macbeth violates the political order, nature goes out of control; fierce storms rage, and animals eat each other. Perhaps the best representative and most important element of the natural and unnatural oppositions in the play appears at the opening scene i.e. the Witches.

In the introduction we encounter the supernatural forces, the three Witches, embarking the stage and plotting maliciously to plant the seeds of evil, which later watered by Lady Macbeth, in Macbeth's mind, and therefore they represent the unnatural; their appearance parallels with stormy weather, lightning and thunder as a sign of chaos and irregular breach in the natural world. The three Witches are introduced as symbols and representatives of evil and darkness. The Witches ascend the stage of *Macbeth* three

times throughout the play and only Macbeth and his friend Banquo see their figures and even talk to them at act one scene three when they call Macbeth "Thane of Glamis," "Thane of Cawdor," and "king hereafter!" (51-53). On the request of Banquo the Witches "speak" to him and prophesy his future as well, they tell him that he is not going to be king himself but "Though shalt get kings" (1.3.70). Yes indeed, Macbeth prophecy has been fulfilled with his wearing the new garment of the Thane of Cawdor and later the gown of the king himself, which is an irrefutable evidence of their power to tell the future.

So are the witches there or they are but "fantastical" creatures found only in imagination; are they of real existence or mere illusion? Are they the root of evil or they are just good-hearted and pure oracles who speak in behalf of the gaged and suppressed population of the kingdom. Are the whole play a mere dream that reveals its dreamer's subconscious desires of aspiring to supreme power, or the events, characters, and the murders that occur in the play are actually occurred and of real existence.

The first thing is the momentous existence of the Witches in the world of *Macbeth*, because they nourish and steer the vehicle of Macbeth's "vaulting ambition" that leads the line of action until the end of the tragedy, thus their existence is essential. And it is obviously stated that the Witches are "supernatural agents of evil" sent by some mysterious wicked power, and in their reversal of the words "Fair is foul, foul is fair" (1.1.12), they "reveal both the capacities and incapacities that the Christian tradition has attributed to devils" (Farnham 81). So far we agree that the Witches are simply evil beings who manipulate and lead Macbeth to his tragic end.

However, what do they really do to condemn them? Only because fierce storms and thunder accompany them by the time they appear, or on the ground that they tempt Macbeth to stir and to take action by foretelling him that he will be king. Yet they never tell him or even insinuate that he is ought to do murders to fulfill his fate, and thus we cannot say that they are totally evil agents. Macbeth says that these witches "Cannot be ill, cannot be good" in response to Banquo's, after telling Macbeth of his new title, saying that these witches are "The instruments of darkness" (1.3.136). When the Witches encounter Macbeth and forecast his fate, then they are the agents of good and not the

agents of the devil, because they come to Macbeth and shake his mind and help him to restore his suppressed notions of seizing the throne, which is his right to get. Yes, his right. Because at the very beginning the wounded Captain informs King Duncan that without the help of "brave" Macbeth and Banquo, there will never be victory; "brave" Macbeth like an eagle "craved out his passage" and "unseamed" the rebel "from the nave to th' chops," (1.2.18-20).

The people in the play are not mentioned at all, and we can assume that the witches are merely the voice of the populace who are suppressed, enslaved and really got upset with the alleged divine right of the King. Therefore, there must be a rebellious act against the king and Macbeth is the best choice, since he is the only one endowed with leadership qualities that manifested themselves in his valor act of defending the kingdom. The witches are described as "Weird" which means fate or destiny, and not merely creepy witches who practice witchcraft to harm other people. And of course destiny relates to God himself; that is the regicide done by the aid of God, who is the controller of destiny or the Weird sisters. In addition, this destiny, undoubtedly, would speak for the common people who are marginalized utterly in the play, and therefore the witches are not some kind of evil agents who aspire to break out the alleged natural chain of being and begin war against God. Concerning the thunder and lightning, that walk abreast with the witches, might symbolize the voice of anger of the obscured and oppressed people who are in desperate need to be rescued from oppression.

King Duncan by contrast to the witches represents the natural order, the source of goodness, and he is God's agent on earth and mainly for this reason the "devilish" Macbeth hesitated before killing him; he simply does not want to miss with God, besides he is "his kinsman and his subject." King Duncan, says Macbeth, is an "even-handed justice" and "that his virtues" will weep for his death like "angels" if Macbeth takes his life. As previously mentioned, God appoints King Duncan and he is responsible to keep the natural order of things on earth as God does in the firmament. But when Macbeth violates the order by his regicide, "confusion made his master piece" (2.3.76), exclaims Macduff coming back from the king's room; the human system collapses and the natural converts to the unnatural because of a breach in the political structure and therefore deity

itself; a blasphemous and inhuman killer intrudes “The Lord's anointed temple” and turns the place to ashes.

It is very easy to see that King Duncan is the most good-natured character in the play, even the murderer (Macbeth) himself speaks of his virtuous and humble character, yet only one significant character in the play does not love him, and even hate him; it is the essential character fate or the Weird sisters and therefore God himself. We said that the king is God's agent on earth, yet God sends his agents (the Witches) to intrigue Macbeth and to tempt him to get something he is not supposed to get, unless this king is never appointed by God but with the aid of some unnatural and even wicked power to ascend the throne and to become king. The divine right of the king now turns into the satanic wrong of the king. At the very beginning of the play act one scene two, we learn of war going on between the kingdom and the *rebellious* army, and the king himself mentions the word “**revolt**” when he speaks to the wounded Captain. This imposes a very crucial question i.e. When do people revolt against a government or a kingdom? Of course, when they are oppressed and suppressed by the king and his henchmen; when they are downtrodden by the hierarchy created by the kingdom in order to keep its feet above the poor and needy wretches of the common people. Moreover, when Macbeth tells his wife "blood will have blood." (3.4.151), indicating that the war has not ended yet and there has to be more and more murders besides King Duncan and his friend Banquo. But this leads us to think that King Duncan did shed blood to get the throne at some time in the past, and therefore the regicide is justifiable, and on these ground King Duncan is the first tyrant who started the blood-shower long time ago.

Lady Macbeth's natural characteristics, that any woman should have, are there in the play to be subverted, undecided and to be unnatural to the feminine structure. A normal woman in the natural world should be religious, pure and submissive to her husband, not the other way round. She should be totally dependent upon her savior (husband), yet Lady Macbeth violates and rejects the feminine conventions and standards for the sake of power; a thing which should only be desired by men who are ready to do anything to get the chair. Things are different in a world so void of stability and unnaturalness. Receiving a letter from Macbeth telling her of his meeting with the Witches and the king's visit,

Lady Macbeth invokes the spirits “That tend on mortal thoughts, [and ask them] unsex [her] here . . .” (1.5.48-79). She is no more interested in the things that make her woman, she gives up her identity and her sex to be filled instead with “direst cruelty” in order to be able to do the heinous deed that her husband weakness "too full o' th' milk of human kindness . . . (1.5.16), might allow him not to proceed in the act. Macbeth, once the 'brave' and hero, is now stripped of his masculine identity and given instead woman's breasts. A mother is supposed to be the most kind-hearted, compassionate and caring creature in the whole world, yet Lady Macbeth spurs these motherly attributes and is ready to be "guilty of the most fiendishly unnatural deed which a mother is capable." (Knights 84). Lady Macbeth speaks unashamedly to Macbeth in act one scene seven of her ability to do the most ruthless act a mother could do to get what she wants, and she asks her husband to leave everything to her, for she is strong enough to do it herself.

LADY MACBETH. I have given suck, and know

How tender 'tis to love the babe that milks me:

I would, while it was smiling in my face,

Have pluck'd my nipple from his boneless gums,

And dash'd the brains out, had I so sworn as you

Have done to this. (62-67)

An important question should not be answered; what is Lady Macbeth? Since she is not a woman, mother, or a wife, nor is she a man or a husband. At the end, Lady Macbeth loses her mind and begins to restore her feminine side when it is too late. She says in one of her sleep-walks:

LADY MACBETH. The Thane of Fife had a wife

Where is She now? What, will these hands ne'er be clean? . . . (5.1.44-45).

She is overwhelmed with guilt and sympathy with the people they have killed, and she begs her “lord, no more o' that . . .” (5.1.46). By contrast to her husband's character that becomes more resolute and determined to proceed in what he begins with.

“Macbeth thane of Glamis” the trustworthy assistant of the king, “Macbeth thane of Cawdor” the brave soldier who defends his King in an impressive valor, or “Macbeth king hereafter” the ‘murderer,’ ‘devilish,’ ‘villain,’ and ‘tyrant’ whose irresistible “vaulting ambition” changes his loyalty to the King to disobedience and his valor to tyranny. From the very beginning we hear words come from King Duncan's holy mouth extolling Macbeth's courage; "O valiant cousin, worthy gentleman!" (1.2.26), the bleeding sergeant, as well, speaks of "brave Macbeth", and the Thane of Ross resembles Macbeth to the "Roman goddess of war", whose "bridegroom" is the "fiercest of warriors" (Mowat and Werstine 12).

The fact that Macbeth is indeed a great leader, who is endowed with leader-like characteristics is crystal clear, and only because of his valor act the kingdom is saved, and not because of the king's cowardice who stays behind the stage clinging to the door of safety. Macbeth might have been killed in the battle while he was defending the kingdom. So who does deserve to rule over the country? The "valiant cousin" or the Divine King? Nonetheless, Macbeth takes actions and kills Duncan who is no more the king after giving up his title to his Malcolm in act 1 scene 4:

DUNCAN. We will establish our estate upon

Our eldest, Malcolm . . . (43-44).

In response to King Duncan's announcement, Macbeth gets angry and asks the king's leave-to-leave. On his way out, he ponders upon the necessity of getting rid of Malcolm, he says:

MACBETH. The Prince of Cumberland! That is a step

On which I must fall down or else o'erleap . . . (1.4.55-56).

Macbeth kills Duncan (the previous king) and the murder being discovered, Malcolm (the current king) flees to England like a rabbit afraid of the lion's claws. Nevertheless, Macbeth does not kill the “step” that he is ought to kill in order to seize the throne, but instead he kills the old man who is about to die himself. After this, Macbeth is described as the most devilish person on earth by almost everyone in the play, especially the lords

and the henchmen who are in favor of Malcolm, merely because he was such a brave and valiant leader who deserves to be the ruler more than anyone else in the play and even more than Malcolm himself who runs away to England to seek their help.

Actually, Macbeth is neither a tyrant nor a king, but he is the most unfortunate victim ever. The agents of darkness, who plant the seeds of evil in his brain earlier in the play, manipulate Macbeth. In addition, he is even instigated by his wife to commit a murder, which he would never dare to do it. He is a very good man who contemplates thoroughly upon the deed and resolves not to take action, but his devilish wife persuades him of the necessity to do so. Lady Macbeth and the Weird sisters are of the same nature and share the same characteristics; when Banquo meets the witches, he exclaims:

BANQUO. You should be women,

And yet your beards forbid me to interpret

That you are so. (1.3.46-48)

Lady Macbeth asks the "spirits" to come and "unsex" her to deceive Macbeth; she is now neither a woman nor a man, exactly like the indefinite-gender of the witches, and they share the same mission and goals; that is to pour the poisonous words in the ear of the powerless victim Macbeth. Eventually, Macbeth falls victim to the biggest victimizer of them all i.e. God. As we said earlier the Weird sisters are representatives of God and they are sexless, a characteristic that Lady Macbeth, the Witches and God have in common. At the end, the Weird sisters desert Macbeth, and his wife dies and leaves him alone to face his tragic end.

Finally and most importantly of the binary oppositions pervaded in the play, is the reality/illusion couple. To begin with, the witches in the play are of great importance to the line of action, for they were the agents of good-evil being, who push Macbeth forward to take action. They meet Macbeth and Banquo in act one scene three and do speak to them. In addition, they tell Macbeth of the king's desire to name him "Thane of Cawdor", and tell Banquo that he will be the father of a line of kings. Moreover, later on, they tell Macbeth to be aware of Macduff who is not born of woman properly, and

therefore he is the only possible threat to him. Hence, their presence is of great importance for *Macbeth*. But when they tell Macbeth of his new title, they do not bring something novel and unknown, because King Duncan himself in act one scene two gives orders to title Macbeth with the Thane of Cawdor, and the witches tell Macbeth of this in act one scene three, which means after the king announcing his intention to title Macbeth with the Than of Cawdor. Concerning the second prophecy of being the king of Scotland, it is only his "vaulting ambition" that makes Macbeth mind imagines things like the Witches, who at that time were persecuted by the king, to be pretexts and false excuses to fulfill his aim of getting the supreme power. When Macbeth reaches the throne by killing the king, Banquo is not satisfied with this because he himself has the same desire to seize the throne and this evidenced in their imagining the witches to be motives for their future actions, but it seems that Macbeth is ready to do anything to get the throne. Banquo's prophecy is not fulfilled in the play and this is another evidence of the witches nonexistence, only in the mind of Macbeth and Banquo, otherwise all the alleged prophecies must have been fulfilled.

We already know that the only characters who see the Weird Sisters are Macbeth and Banquo, but why? Because they are the only men who are endowed with characteristics that enable them to get the throne, and deep down in their mind they crave to get the chair, and thus they invent the Witches in order to take action. Macbeth, for sure, deserves to seize the throne more than Banquo, because of his brave and shrewd character, also his resolution to take action to get what he craves for, and this is very clear when Macbeth is in rapt of the witches' prophecy:

MACBETH. If chance will have me king, why, chance may

Crown me

Without my stir. (1.3.157-159)

Night, without any shadow of doubt, is the most lovable company and assistance of the most heart-less, barbaric, and ruthless deeds and actions on earth. The very first reference to darkness is in the opening scene; the first appearance of the witches who bring with them a stormy weather, lightning and thunder. Whenever somebody wishes to

do an immoral act or to commit a crime, he/she conjectures night to cloak in his/ her evil deeds. Lady Macbeth bids the "thick night" to come and shroud "the dunnest smoke of heel", in order not for heaven to see the wound her knife makes. And even Macbeth when he resolves to murder Banquo, he asks the "selling night" to come to hide his criminal act. As opposed to night, day is the source of light and goodness, and it is the time when the agents of good are at work.

Yet, night is not always associated with darkness, fiends, agents of evil and Satan, but it also means silence, loneliness, sleep, and dreams (Ferber 136). Yes indeed, at the opening scene we encounter night with supernatural forces that exist only in dreams and imagination. In night all creatures are supposed to be in bed, except the silver moon. We hear not a stir or action, nor can we witness a murder or a treason. At night, Macbeth is supposed to be in bed holding his wife to his bosom and telling her of his love and passion.

To round things out, it seems that Shakespeare's *Macbeth* is the best expression for the modern deconstruction. The play, even though written in 1606, is as modern as deconstruction itself; everything in the play is turned upside down, which, in turns, shakes our own world as well, and bids us to think in different ways. The ceaseless fountain of meanings seems as generous as never, and the ocean of language is much deeper than any period ever. Surely enough, deconstruction opens for us countless ways to deepen our understanding for literature and the whole world that we live in as well. Yet, its inability to reach a final conclusion of meaning, makes it avoidable and undesirable by many critics and teachers of literature. To leave it open ended is their aim and mine too. By now, hopefully, the ambiguity of deconstruction is no more ambiguous, and the difficulty of its application is no more difficult.

Works Cited

1. Bressler, Charles E. *Literary criticism: An Introduction to Theory and practice*. New Jersey: Prentice-Hall. Ins,1994. Print.
2. Farnham, Willard. "The Witches". *Shakespeare's Tragic Frontier: The World of His Final Tragedies*. Oxford: Basil Blackwell and Mott Ltd., 1973. 80-82. Print.
3. Knights, L C. . "Macbeth". *Some Shakespearean Themes*. Stanford, CA: Stanford U P and London, Chatto and Windus Ltd., 1959. 120-142. Print.
4. Mowat, Barbara A., and Paul Werstine. Eds. *The Tragedy of Macbeth*. By William Shakespeare. New York: WSP- Filger,1992. Print.
5. Tyson, Louis. *Critical Theory Today: a User-Friendly Guide*. 2nd ed. New York: Rutledge- Louis Tayson, 2006. PDF file.
6. Waller, Gary. *Decentering the Bard: Shakespeare and Deconstruction*. New York: Peter Lang, 1988. 21-45. PDF file.
7. Witek, Stephen. *A Brief history of Deconstruction in Shakespeare's Criticism*. [Eng.]: n.p., n.d.: 1-11. PDF file.

Works Consulted

1. Hawkes, Terence. Ed. *Twentieth Century Interpretation of Macbeth: A Collection of Critical Essays*. Englewood Cliffs: Prentice-Hall 1977. Print.
2. Quintus, Joshua. *Macbeth: Study Guide*. No.p.: Spark Notes LLC, 2014. PDF file.
- 3- The Land of Macbeth. *Seven Essays of Classic Macbeth criticism*. N.p.: n.d., no. d.. PDF File.
- 4- Van Niekerk, Marthinus Christoffel. *Shakespearian Play: Deconstructive Readings of The Merchant of Venice, The Tempest, Measure for Measure and Hamlet*. Dis Np.: U of Pretoria etd., 2003. PDF file.

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Lighthouse Academy Syria

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